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TABLE OF ABBREVIATIONS

DoA: Description of Action

FB: Facebook

KPI: Key Performance Indicator

xAPI: Experience API

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The investment behind the BEACONING project requires tangible and perceivable results. The Dissemination and Communication plan (D2.1) provided the BEACONING strategy to support all project partners in obtaining and maximizing this impact.

The document collects all the information on the dissemination activities carried out during the first 18 months of the project. This includes articles published in high impact scientific journals, papers presented at international conferences, workshops and other dissemination events. The dissemination results in 18 months time will be compared against the KPIs established in T2.1.

The current results show that the project exceeds the expected results from the DoA and that all the main KPIs have been successfully achieved. We have already identified one success case and we are in the process of collecting more from the consortium. We have also identified some minor shortcomings and we are proposing some corrective actions.

The current figures included in this document were obtained on June 29th 2017.

This document will be updated in “D2.4. Dissemination results 2” with dissemination activities of months 19 to 36.

1 INTRODUCTION

As described in “D2.1 Dissemination and Communication plan”, the BEACONING project requires tangible and perceivable results, where the strategy to maximize this impact was described specifying five main objectives:

1. **Increase awareness.**
2. **Contribute to the advancement of BEACONING R&D .**
3. **Promote open access of and stimulate interest.**
4. **Promote the adoption of the project outcomes.**
5. **Inform decision and policy makers in education.**

Notice that the dissemination has been very challenging as the project needed to create awareness and impact at the same time that the BEACONING technology and products were being designed and created.

1.1 ROLE OF THIS DELIVERABLE IN THE PROJECT

This deliverable provides results of how the project’s goals for dissemination and business communication activities have been achieved in the first 18 months of the project.

This document is also an evaluation on how the project is progressing during the first half of the project and what open issues about the dissemination (e.g. specific stakeholders not being reached) and what corrective actions should be taken to address those issues in the following 18 months.

1.2 APPROACH

This document has been prepared following the Dissemination and Communication Plan (D2.1) which, in turn, was an extension and improvement of the guidelines set in the BEACONING DoA.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

The deliverable is structured as follows:

Section 2 describes in detail the Key Performance Indicators and the achieved levels applied in months 1-18 to benchmark the of the Dissemination and Communication Plan.

Section 3 describes the main success cases in terms of dissemination reachment for different platforms.

Section 4 provides some conclusions of the dissemination results.

We also include three **Appendices** with more detailed information about:

Section 5 provides additional Twitter statistics.

Section 6 provides information about the Zenodo Community.

Section 7 provides more details of BEACONING events.

2 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPI)

To quantify the quality of the dissemination activities and achievements, a number of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were defined as a reference during the project's lifetime. The main goal of these KPIs is to measure and track the impact of project outcomes.

At this point, we analyse for each KPI is current state at month 18. Currently, **more than 100 dissemination activities** have been carried out where the main stakeholders in most of the countries have been reached.

2.1 DIGITAL COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Project website

General description of the structure and content of the BEACONING website can be found in "D2.2 Project Branding and Website Start-up".

KPIs defined in DoA for the project website and their expected values were:

Website KPI	M7	M19	M25	M36	5 years
Page hits	500	5000	10000	30000	60000
Unique visitors	20	300	500	2000	4000
Incoming links	14	37	47	67	100
Countries made aware	10	15	25	50	60

Table 1. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING Website.

Figure 1. BEACONING Website main page at <http://beaconing.eu/>

Current state at month 18 from statistics from Google Analytics and Google Webmaster Tools for the number of links to Beaconing portal:

Website KPI	M18
Page hits	23687

Unique visitors	4368
Return visitors*	2942
Incoming links	450 links from 76 domains
Countries made aware	101
User accounts on website*	44
Post in events section*	80
Post in blog section*	63

Table 2. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING Website reached at month 18

*Were not originally specified in DoA.

Blog Posts

<input type="checkbox"/> Title	Author	Tags		Date
BEACONING Consortium workshop in Bucharest	Tomasz Skupinski	—	—	Published 2017/06/27
Half way there partners meeting — Draft	Tomasz Skupinski	—	—	Last Modified 2017/06/21
DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SKILLS IN INTERDISCIPLINARY CONTEXT	Marius Preda	—	—	Published 2017/06/16
Nesesiitatea utilizării platformelor de e-Learning în procesul integrării copiilor cu nevoi speciale	Marius Preda	—	—	Published 2017/06/16
Inquiry-based Learning in Science Lessons	Marius Preda	—	—	Published 2017/06/16
Wordles word world – could word clouds aid gamified lesson design?	Theo Lim	—	—	Published 2017/06/12
Integration Workshop at INESC	Hans Free Computing	—	—	Published 2017/06/12
Beaconing workshop at EC-T&E 2017	Massimiliano Cazzaniga	—	—	Published 2017/06/12
Beaconing at #DisruptiveBytes – EU-Funded Game-based projects	Jayne Beaufoy	—	—	Published 2017/06/09
BEACONING Demo Workshop in Coventry	Jayne Beaufoy	—	—	Published 2017/06/09
Using a videogame to teach people with intellectual disabilities how to use the subway system of Madrid	Baltaz	—	—	Published 2017/05/24
Beaconing selected within the VERTIGO program	admin	—	—	Published 2017/05/03
Possible link with TeSLA	samab75	—	—	Published 2017/04/19
STEM Approaches in Romanian Schools	Marius Preda	—	—	Published 2017/04/12

Figure 2. BEACONING Website blog posts.

Events

<input type="checkbox"/> Title	Author	Date
ASME IDETC/CIE 2017	Theo Lim	Published 2017.06/28
CITB invited presentation	Theo Lim	Published 2017.06/27
(no title)	Tomasz Skupinski	Published 2017.06/27
(no title)	Tomasz Skupinski	Published 2017.06/27
BEACONING at IFIP ICEC 2017	Nadera Sultana	Published 2017.06/23
BEACONING at ISAGA 2017	Nadera Sultana	Published 2017.06/23
BEACONING at ISL 2017	Nadera Sultana	Published 2017.06/23
BEACONING at IEEE SeGAH 2016	Nadera Sultana	Published 2017.06/23
BEACONING at GALA 2016	Nadera Sultana	Published 2017.06/23
BEACONING at eLSE 2016	Nadera Sultana	Published 2017.06/23
BEACONING at ASME 2016	Nadera Sultana	Published 2017.06/23
BEACONING at Entertainment Computing – ICEC 2016	Nadera Sultana	Published 2017.06/23
BEACONING at APMS 2016	Nadera Sultana	Published 2017.06/23
Learning Analytics Workshop	Joao Tiago Neto Jacob	Published 2017.06/21
Creative Colab 17 – Location-Based Games Workshop	Joao Tiago Neto Jacob	Published 2017.06/21

Figure 3. BEACONING website events (for full list of events see Appendix 3).

Social media

KPIs defined in DoA for social media impact and their expected values were:

Social Media KPI	M7	M19	M25	M36	5 years
Number of posts	10	50	100	200	300
Number of subscribers	30	200	500	750	1000
Interactions (FB Likes, Twitter Retweet, Share, etc.)	20	100	200	400	600
Reach (prints, visits, etc.)	500	5000	10000	50000	75000

Table 3. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING Social Media channels

Current state at month 18, obtained from Facebook stats:

Social Media KPI	M18
Number of posts	156 (Facebook) 471 (Tweets)
Number of subscribers	370 (Facebook)

	476 (Twitter followers)
Interactions (FB Likes, Twitter Retweet, Share, etc.)	373 Facebook likes
Reach (prints, visits, etc.)	>13900 views*

Table 4. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING Social Media channels reached at month 18

*Only in the last 3 months. Top 5 seen tweets from BEACONING Twitter collect more than 3000 views. More details are provided in Appendix 1.

The Twitter account has been linked to the Facebook page to simplify the publication of news and posts, so any contribution from the BEACONING twitter account also appears in the Facebook page.

Figure 4. Screenshot of the BEACONING Facebook page, with detail of page likes and followers.

Figure 5. Screenshot of the BEACONING Twitter main page.

Figure 6. Screenshot of BEACONING twitter statistics about tweets and retweets.

More detailed Twitter statistics are presented in the Appendix 1.

Newsletters

KPIs defined in DoA for newsletters impact and their expected values were:

Newsletter KPI	M7	M19	M25	M36	5 years
Number of newsletters	1	3	4	6	10
Number of subscribers	100	200	250	600	1000

Table 5. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING newsletters

Current state at month 18, obtained as number of newsletters published and number of subscribers (calculated as count of distinct IPs having read at least one of the five newsletters):

Newsletter KPI	M18
Number of newsletters	5
Number of subscribers	647

Table 6. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING newsletters reached at month 18

2.2 ACADEMIC ACTIVITIES

2.2.1 Publications

Scientific papers, Conferences, Newspaper articles, etc.

KPIs defined in DoA for publications (e.g. scientific papers, conferences, newspaper articles, etc.) impact and their expected values were:

Publication KPI	M7	M19	M25	M36	5 years
Conference papers		9	15	25	30
Journal papers		1	2	8	12
Newspaper articles	1	3	4	5	10
Books				1	

Table 7. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING academic papers

For publications dissemination, a Zenodo BEACONING open repository has been created (accessible at https://zenodo.org/communities/beaconing_eu/). All the scientific publications having BEACONING in acknowledgments will appear there as open documents (either the final version when possible or a final draft or author personal copy).

Current state at month 18, from Zenodo webpage for H2020 BEACONING PROJECT Community:

Publication KPI	M18
Conference papers	25
Journal papers	4
Books	2 sections
Poster*	1
Other*	1

Table 8. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING academic papers reached at month 18

*Were not specific on original D2.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan.

Figure 7. Screenshot of Zenodo BEACONING project repository.

Figure 8. Screenshot of Zenodo publications.

2.2.2 Dissemination events

Summary of the number of dissemination events by partner:

Figure 9. Number of dissemination events by partner.

Even if not all dissemination events report the number of people involved, currently, at least with the provided numbers, **more than 1000 people have been reached by BEACONING events**. For more details, refer to the dissemination events on Appendix 3 (all details about those events including links and photos can be found on the website). This number is even bigger taking into account technology validation experiences and pilots.

Among all those events, it stands out that BEACONING was nominated for the Best Education Project Award in the Gamification World Congress 2016.

Conferences, seminars, workshops

KPIs defined in DoA for conferences, seminars and workshops impact and their expected values were:

Workshop KPI	M7	M19	M25	M36	5 years
Number of conferences, seminars and workshops		7	7	9	18
Number of attendants (each region)		50		100	150

Table 9. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING conferences, seminars and workshops

Current state at month 18:

Workshop KPI	M18
Number of conferences	39
Number of seminars	5
Number of workshop	15

Table 10. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING conferences, seminars and workshops reached at month 18

Full details in the Appendix 3. Examples of participation in conferences are:

- International Conference on Entertainment Computing (ICEC) 2016
- eLSE Conference 2017
- 7th International Conference on Software Development and Technologies for Enhancing Accessibility and Fighting Info-exclusion 2016
- IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON) 2017

Keynote presentations and Lectures

KPIs defined in DoA for keynote presentations and lectures impact and their expected values were:

Keynotes and lectures KPI	M7	M19	M25	M36	5 years
Number of keynotes and lectures	3	15	25	40	50
Number of attendants (cumulative)	60	300	500	800	1000

Table 11. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING participation in keynotes and lectures

Current state at month 18:

Keynotes and lectures KPI	M18
Number of keynotes	11

Table 12. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING participation in keynotes and lectures reached at month 18

Full details in the Appendix 3. Examples of keynotes in conferences are:

- REV International Conference 2016
- GamiLearn 2017
- European Conference on Game Based Learning (ECGBL) 2016
- The International Conference on E-learning and Games (Edutainment) 2017

2.3 FACE TO FACE ACTIVITIES

"On-site" visits and stakeholder involvement

KPIs defined in DoA for on-site visits and stakeholder involvement impact and their expected values were:

Stakeholder involvement KPIs	M7	M19	M25	M36	5 years
Number of industrial partners	5	10	25	30	50
Number of end-user intermediaries	4	10	25	30	50
Number of research organizations	7	10	25	30	50
Number of interviews (industry-level)		10		30	
Number of focus groups	14	20	30	50	

Table 13. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING stakeholder involvement

Current state at month 18:

It is described in the dissemination activities (in Appendix 3 and with all the details on the website including photos and url links). The stakeholders involvement in the project has included educational authorities, including ministries of education and local and regional authorities; teachers and practitioners; schools and vocational training facilities; students.

Contact with related EU projects

KPIs defined in DoA for events related with other EU projects impact and their expected values were:

Project networking KPI	M7	M19	M25	M36	5 years
Number of events	3	15	25	40	50

Number of attendants (cumulative)	60	300	500	800	1000
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Table 14. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING contact with related EU projects

Current state at month 18:

Contact with other projects has been greatly simplified by the Digital Learning Meeting organized by the EU in March 27th in Luxemburg which reunited participants from 30 projects.

Main contact has been established with the following EU projects:

- Tesla
- Rage
- Jamtoday
- Crowd4roads
- Magellan

Currently, there is a closed collaboration with RAGE as the architecture developed for RAGE is being reused, extended and improved in BEACONING. The technology developed at BEACONING in terms of game trackers, teacher dashboards and visualizations, and extension proposed for geolocalization to the Serious Games xAPI Profile, will be contributed back to the RAGE infrastructure and ecosystem.

Partners are also looking for synergies with other local, regional and national projects related with the use of games in education at large. For instance, UCM has established a cooperation with other projects such as DownTown (Francisco de Vitoria University), Telefónica Chair on Digital Education and Serious Games and with the Network of Excellence eMadrid in the Madrid region. This is also the case in other countries such as France and the UK.

2.4 OTHER ACTIONS AND COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

As described in D2.1, we are also using secondary channels for creating impact. Examples of these are presented below.

2.4.1 Promotional videos

YouTube promotional videos at the BEACONING Channel that are also linked from the BEACONING website:

Title	YouTube account	Visualizations	URL
Beaconing promo video	Imaginary	553	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dJA7ohE9X8g
What is Beaconing about?	Beaconing Channel	145	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=33my7ilwcOU
Beaconing challenges with ORT France	Beaconing Channel	57	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vMxhE5-0nZI
Beaconing challenges with SEBIT	Beaconing Channel	29	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KLnT8LUZ1Vg

Beaconing challenges with INESC TEC & SIVECO	Beaconing Channel	40	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9hCwfDx65U
Beaconing challenges with IMAGINARY & PLAYSOFIT	Beaconing Channel	23	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TEx96FNYlh8
Beaconing challenges with Heriot-Watt University	Beaconing Channel	33	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hc7jXHH1bhc
Beaconing challenges with UCM	Beaconing Channel	21	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iRnBS3oIA2c
Beaconing challenges with Coventry University	Beaconing Channel	66	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7a3B8CL1q68
Beaconing challenges with Ifinity	Beaconing Channel	23	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=68dPg3O6rl4

Table 15. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING contact with related EU projects

Figure 10. Screenshot of the BEACONING promo video on YouTube.

2.4.2 SlideShare

SlideShare has been promoted as the preferred channel for slide distribution. Some partners have their own personal SlideShare accounts with presentations about BEACONING having a great impact, as the ones specified below.

Figure 11. Screenshot of a BEACONING project short SlideShare presentation, accessible at <https://es.slideshare.net/sarnab75/beaconing-2minute-summary-for-dgconnect-event-lux>

Figure 12. Screenshot of a BEACONING project short SlideShare presentation, accessible at <https://www.slideshare.net/BaltasarFernandezManjon/rev-gaming-learning-analytics-rage-and-beaconing>

2.4.3 ResearchGate

ResearchGate has been proposed as a channel for dissemination of scientific publications and presentations. A BEACONING project page has been also created, accessible at <https://www.researchgate.net/project/BEACONING>.

Figure 13. Screenshot of ResearchGate BEACONING project page.

Figure 14. Screenshot of ResearchGate BEACONING article uploaded by Baltasar Fernandez UCM.

2.4.4 Other Events

On the BEACONING website, there are other dissemination events and activities reported (apart from the previously described conferences, workshop, keynotes, etc.).

Their current state at month 18:

Other events KPI	M18
Number of presentations	14
Number of press activities	11
Number of talks	10
Number of meetings	3
Number of blog posts	3
Number of round tables	2
Number of focus groups	2
Number of lessons	1
Number of webinars	1

Number of radio events	1
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Table 16. KPIs and target values for the BEACONING participation in other events reached at month 18

Figure 15. Summary of all BEACONING dissemination events.

3 EXAMPLE ENGAGEMENT AND IMPACT CASES

As part of the dissemination and communication activities, the process of identifying example impact cases by partners is still ongoing and these will inform methods and procedures that can be replicated in different countries and contexts. This section showcases two examples related to technology validation (unit and integrated respectively) with stakeholders. The small scale pilot setup as described in Deliverable 5.3 will be key to the immediate testing and validation of our components and integration process. Please also refer to the events page on the BEACONING website (also described in section 2.1 and appendix 3) of our existing and upcoming engagement/events with the stakeholders, which will be key for recording our impact cases as part of the dissemination and communication process.

3.1 EXAMPLE CASE OF TECHNOLOGY VALIDATION - UCM

This example case demonstrates technology validation that are being adopted and adapted for the BEACONING platform as well as the initiative to collaborate with existing local projects. UCM as lead of the learning analytics task, has collaborated with the DownTown project providing **the technology and the experimental design for the scientific validation experiment to test a serious game**. Specifically, UCM incorporated the analytics system to collect data during the experiment to the preexisting game that was produced by CEIEC (Center for Research and Innovation in Knowledge Management), an Institute of Francisco de Vitoria University, in cooperation with Down Madrid Association.

The experiment, conducted in May 2017, involved 45 people with different cognitive disabilities (mainly Down Syndrome) and is a pilot of BEACONING.

The serious game, *Downtown, A Subway Adventure*, has had a great impact:

- **Madrid metro internal TV.** A video promoting the serious game *DownTown* appeared on the subway interval television from May 29th to June 3rd. The number of passengers of the metro each day is more than 1 million people. This video already describes the experiment and the data analytics capture process proposed by BEACONING, even if BEACONING is not directly mentioned.

Figure 16. Screenshot of the video in the metro internal TV.

- **Television:** The game has appeared on *Telemadrid*, the main local television in Madrid [[link to the piece of news](#)].
- **Press.** The game has appeared on multiple journals and press media, such as:
 - *El Mundo*, major journal in Spain [[link to the piece of news](#)].
 - *Servimedia*, agency of news [[link to the piece of news](#)].
- **Social media.**
 - *Twitter.* The validation experiment has produced several tweets, including one of the official Twitter account of the Complutense University of Madrid, which

has more than 60.000 followers. Only this tweet produced more than 50 retweets and more than 50 likes.

Figure 17. Screenshot of a related tweet by Complutense University of Madrid.

- **Award:**

- After the experiment carried out with the game, and based on the obtained exposure, the serious game *Downtown, A Subway Adventure* was proposed to and received the Discapnet award to the best ICT application for people with special needs. The award was given by the Queen of Spain [[link to piece of news on royal house website](#)].

3.2 EXAMPLE CASE OF TECHNOLOGY VALIDATION – ATS

This example case demonstrates the process for collecting feedback from stakeholders with regards to the integrated BEACONING prototype and the corresponding components as well as the engagement with stakeholders from the schools, industry and research. ATS, BEACONING' s lead teachical partner (WP4 lead) has organized a BEACONING Demo Session at the International Scientific Conference on "eLearning and Software for Education" (eLSE 2017) in collaboration with BEACONING partners and the Romanian Partnership Lab of the Advanced Distributed Learning Initiative. The demo session has showcased the BEACONING core components: the Game Plot (Meta game); the Minigames; the Location-based componnet; the Authoring Tool; the User Interface.

Figure 18. The BEACONING Metagame projected on the screen from an Android device

Figure 19. Demo of a BEACONING Minigame challenge

Figure 20. Demo of BEACONING Metagame narratives

Figure 21. Demo of BEACONING Authoring Tool

A questionnaire has been distributed in order to collect feedback on the demo versions of the BEACONING components. 11 teachers and 12 students have participated in the experiment. ATS offered a phone and a tablet as prizes for students and teachers.

Figure 22. Winners of the BEACONING demo session prizes

Figure 23. Number of students playing DGs by frequency

Figure 24. Winning team of the “Follow the path” challenge

A dedicated context-aware challenge for outdoors with an indoor last quest was created for the event by Geomotion and participants were asked to play the game “Robot Treasure Hunt”. ATS has offered a prize to the first student who successfully completed the game. Some of the students formed ad-hoc groups to find clues faster, and the winner was a group of students that traveled almost 400km to attend the demo session. The outcome of the demo session has proved the user friendliness of the BEACONING solution for users that are using it for the very first time, without any training.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS

Dissemination of the project can be considered a success, as **all the KPIs have been attained** and in many cases have been clearly exceeded. From our previous description, it has been demonstrated that **BEACONING has been able to make a clear impact** and now it is recognized as one of the new EU innovative research projects using games and gamification approaches.

Still, there is room for improvement and BEACONING needs to continue and extend the dissemination effort. This task now will be simplified as the project is beginning to have the first products that can be used for pilots in schools, which will have even a greater impact.

All partners need to better understand the dissemination effort and some of them need to be more active in the process. Also, we need to improve the reporting of dissemination events and activities to better identify the stakeholders involved and the number of people reached. We will provide more detailed guidelines to the partners about how to report them.

As described in “D2.1 Dissemination and Communication plan”, we are now in the process of identifying more success cases that can be replicated on different countries and contexts. Currently, we have an open call in the consortium for partners to propose their success cases in their countries.

APPENDIX 1: TWITTER STATISTICS

Figure 25. Tweets views in the last 3 months for BEACONING Twitter account.

Figure 26. Followers in the last month for BEACONING Twitter account.

Tweet	Views	Interactions
Beaconing H2020 @BeaconingEU · 14 jun Game-based learning #seriousgames game-learn.com/baltasar-ferna... @BeaconingEU @RageAppliedGame <small>Ver la Actividad del Tweet</small>	757	24
Beaconing H2020 @BeaconingEU · 12 jun WKS on authoring game-based #STEM learning experiences beaconing.eu/events/worksho... #PervasiveLearning #edtech @ECTEL17 <small>Ver la Actividad del Tweet</small>	675	24
Beaconing H2020 @BeaconingEU · 14 jun Evaluating a #cyberbullying #videogame in schools collecting #xAPI data. Already 200 students! One session more to go in Zaragoza. twitter.com/BaltaFM/status... <small>Ver la Actividad del Tweet</small>	605	4
Beaconing H2020 @BeaconingEU · 10 jun Dissemination about #gamification & #seriousgames in a radio program. What else with @baltafm1 @BeaconingEU @gamilearn @cive2017 twitter.com/BaltaFM/status... <small>Ver la Actividad del Tweet</small>	603	12
Beaconing H2020 @BeaconingEU · 20 abr Possible link between @teslaprojecteu and #H2020 @BeaconingEU beaconing.eu/2017/04/19/pos... via @sarnab75 #Gamification #gbl <small>Ver la Actividad del Tweet</small>	516	13

Figure 27. Top 5 tweets for BEACONING Twitter account.

APPENDIX 2: BEACONING ZENODO COMMUNITY

The main page of the community of the H2020 BEACONING Project can be found in:

https://zenodo.org/communities/beaconing_eu/

Figure 29. Main page of BEACONING community in zenodo.

All publications from the project should appear there. You can log in with GitHub, ORCID or create an account with your email address and password.

UPLOADING DETAILS

From the main upload page (https://zenodo.org/deposit/new?c=beaconing_eu) you can add your contributions to the project.

Firstly you have to add your file and click on “Start upload” to correctly upload the file.

Figure 30. Upload page. First, choose file to upload.

Below you can complete the file details:

- Upload type. In the case of publications and images, you have to select their type in the drop-down list below.
- Basic information: DOI (optional), publication date, title, authors, description, keywords (optional) and additional notes.
- Access right and license.

- Communities: H2020 BEACONING Project.

The following sections (funding, related/alternate identifiers, contributors, references, journal, conference, book/report/chapter, thesis and subjects) are optional, but please consider to add the suitable information of your file for more detailed publication.

After saving the upload details, you can upload the contribution. At that moment, an email will be sent to the UCM coordinator who will complete the curation process and accept the upload.

Figure 31. Upload page with details completed.

Figure 32. View of the contribution after upload.

APPENDIX 3: BEACONING EVENTS

All details about these dissemination events including links, documents and photos can be found on the BEACONING website.

When	Where	Partner	Work Package	Title	Impact	Target Group
20160126	COVUNI	All Partners	All	BEACONING press release		Public, Private, Researchers, Teachers, Students
20160210	Romania	ATS	WP2, WP4	BEACONING press release in Romania		Public, Private, Researchers, Teachers, Students
20160401	Barcelona	15 partners	All	BEACONING Workshop on stakeholder analysis and inventory of existing infrastructures		
20160420	Targoviste, RO	ATS	WP2, WP4	BEACONING at Multidisciplinary Science and Technology Research Institute of UVT		Teachers, Students
20160421	Bucharest, RO	ATS		BEACONING presented at the eLSE Conference 2016		
20160509	Lisbon	INESC TEC Porto		BEACONING dissemination at Eurographics 2016		
20160205	On-line	SIVCO Romania		Disruptive Media Learning Lab launches BEACONING project		
20160517	Oxford, UK	Hands Free Computing		Assistive Technology Exhibition & Conference		
20160201	Online	Hands Free Computing		Hands Free chosen to develop accessible features for the E5.9m EU funded BEACONING Project		
20160323	BIP bulletin INESC TEC - online	INESC TEC		Press release		
20160101	Press	HWU		BEACONING at HWU		
20160629	Academia of Creteil,	ORT		BEACONING presentation to representatives of high schools in Paris		

	Thiais, France					
20160719	Paris, ORT premises	ORT, COVUNI		"BeaconiZation" of Scenarios		
20160630	Aston University, Birmingham, UK	Hands Free Computing Ltd		Hands Free Computing promotes BEACONING at the aDShe annual conference		
20160622	Portaria, Greece	ORT FRANCE		BEACONING project presentation at the ENH2016 Conference		
20160810	on-line	SIVCO Romania		Teachers, pupils and parents in Romania are invited to be part of the European research & innovation project BEACONING		
20160822	Charlotte, North Carolina, SUA	ATS, BIBA, HWU	WP2, WP4	BEACONING at IDETC/CIE Conference, ASME		Researchers
20160928	Santander - London	Hands Free Computing		STEM..a roadmap to success! - Key event addressing the recruitment of students in STEM subjects		
20161122	Choisy Le Roi, France	ORT		ORT Choisy le Roi, BEACONING presentation		
20161122	Paris, France	ORT		Presentation to stakeholders: Teachers of Academia of Versailles		
20161128	Orlando, Florida	ATS	WP2, WP4	BEACONING presented by ATS at I/ITSEC 2016 - Orlando, Florida		Researchers
20161206	Utrecht, the Netherlands	BIBA, Coventry University		BEACONING presented by BIBA and Coventry University at Gala 2016		
20161207	Port of Spain, Trinidad and Tobago	Coventry University	2	Play for Outstanding Results	Playful and gameful approach being adapted and adopted by target audience	Private and public bodies

20161027	Madrid	Coventry University	2	Gamification World Congress	BEACONING nominated for the Best Education Project award	Gamification community (industry, education and health)
20161202	Vila Real, Portugal	Coventry University	2	7th International Conference on Software Development and Technologies for Enhancing Accessibility and Fighting Info-exclusion		Private and public
20170509	Pori, Finland	Coventry University	2	Keynote at Gamifin 2017, Pori, Finland		Private and Public
20170626	Bournemouth, UK	Coventry University	2	Keynote at The International Conference on E-learning and Games (Edutainment) 2017		Private and public
20160407	Real Colegio Complutense at Harvard, Harvard University, Boston, USA	UCM	WP2,	Gaming Learning Analytics: using data for improving serious games applicability at the New technologies in Education	30	Researchers, General Public
20160226	REV International Conference, Madrid, Spain Invited Keynote	UCM	WP2, WP4	Gaming Learning Analytics: How projects RAGE and BEACONING are improving Serious Games Applicability	75	Researchers
20160222	Festival for Digital Health, UCL, London	UCM	WP2, WP4	Games for health: Do they actually work?	75	Researchers, Students
20170225	Facultad de Informática, UCM, Madrid	UCM	WP2, WP4	Semana de la Informática UCM - Invited talk on H2020 research projects for Computer Science Students	30	Students
20160301	Universidad de Valladolid,	UCM	WP2, WP4	Investigación en tecnología educativa: juegos serios y analíticas de aprendizaje	30	Researchers, Students

	Valladolid, Spain					
20160421	UNED, Madrid, Spain	UCM	WP2, WP4	Nuevos desarrollos en tecnologías educativas: juegos serios y analíticas de aprendizaje	45	Researchers, Students, Teachers
20160520	Madrid, Spain	UCM	WP2	Juegos Serios	50	Researchers, Students, General Public
20161006	Paisley, Scotland, UK	UCM	WP2, WP4	Gaming Learning Analytics: Contributing to the Serious Games Ecosystem	110	Researchers, Students, Teachers
20161108	Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha, Ciudad Real, Spain	UCM	WP2	Aplicaciones de los juegos serios	80	Students, Researchers
20160712	UNED, Madrid, Spain	UCM	WP2, WP4	Nuevos contenidos educativos: de la narración a la interacción y las analíticas de aprendizaje	40	Students, Researchers, Teachers
20161122	Facultad de Informática, UCM, Madrid	UCM	WP2	Juegos Serios: un futuro profesional en el mundo de los videojuegos	102	Students, Researchers, Industry
20160916	Trento, Italy, Key note	BIBA/KTH	2	Gamification of Mobility and Transport Planning. Opportunities, challenges and limits	Around 50 participants from authorities, cities, and research interested in user participation and gamification	Authorities and researchers
20161215	Piacenza	imaginary		Project presentation to the school's stakeholders: news from Italy.		
20161024	IRETETH in Volos, Greece	ORT France		BEACONING project presentation at CERTH		Researchers
20161201	University of Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro,	INESC TEC		BEACONING by INESC TEC at DSAI 2016		Research community

	Vila Real - Portugal					
20170215	Coventry University	Coventry University	WP2	Remix Play Summit, 15th Feb 2017		Universities, Scademics, Students, HE, FE
20160616	Spain - Conference	Geomotion Games	WP2	The BEACONING project at #SpinUOC	300 people	Educational Community. Secondary Schools. Universities. Academic. Industry.
20170116	London - Conference Keynote	Geomotion Games	WP2	Real-life games	250	Gaming Industry
20170203	Barcelona - Meetup	Geomotion Games	WP2	Geolocation to expand Gamification to new industries	50	Stakeholders: Gamification
20170306	Strasbourg, France	ORT	WP5	ORT Workshop for Teachers at ORT Strasbourg school		
20170303	Hotel Impiana, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia	Imaginary	WP2	ICCE 2017 - 3rd International Conference on Creative Education	Dissemination and Raising Awareness of BEACONING	International Practitioners and Education Innovators
20170224	Conference - Universidad Complutense de Madrid (Madrid)	Geomotion Games	WP2	Location based games: reinventing the way we Play & Learn	500	Education Stakeholders
20170606	ILEC Conference Centre and IBIS London Earls Court, 47 Lillie Road, London, SW6 1UD	Hands Free Computing		The Assistive Technology Exhibition and Conference		Aimed at disability professionals involved in post 16 education and the work place, ATEC is a one-day event that allows you to listen to and meet with experts, solution providers and

						other like-minded people
20170306	Strasbourg, France	ORT	WP5	ORT Strasbourg school workshop	ORT Strasbourg school	Teachers
20170307	Montreuil, Paris, France	ORT	WP5	ORT Montreuil school workshop		Teachers
20170309	Paris, France	ORT	WP2	EDUSPOT - BEACONING - A mobile and pervasive environment		Educational professional
20170526	Barcelona - La Salle (Ramon Llull University)	GEOMOTION GAMES	WP2	Location-based Serious Games. Seminar and Workshop		Master on Multimedia and Serious Games creation
20171116	Seville, Spain	ORT France		Abstract submission for the ICERI2017 conference		
20170806	August 6-9, 2017 in Cleveland, Ohio	HWU	WP3, WP4, WP5	ASME International Design Engineering Technical Conferences & Computers and Information in Engineering Conference (IDETC/CIE 2017)	Accessible game-based approaches for the masses - from virtual to real world use.	Engineers, TVET, ICT
20170912	EC-TEL conference, Tallinn (Estonia)	imaginary	WP2	Workshop on authoring game-based STEM learning experiences	To disseminate the BEACONING project to a relevant audience while creating new gamified experiences useful for the project.	Teachers, learning designers, researchers involved in TEL, learning experts
20170602	Heriot-Watt University	HWU	WP3, WP4, WP5	Robotics seminars - Edinburgh Centre for Robotics	Facilitating interaction between robotics related researchers and others, ultimately strengthen the Edinburgh Centre for Robotics.	Engineers, ICT, HCI, Robotics, Autonomous Systems
20170606	ILEC Conference Centre and IBIS London Earls Court, 47 Lillie Road, London, SW6 1UD	Hands Free Computing	4	ATEC Conference London	ATEC showcases excellence in assistive technology that removes barriers to learning and work	STEM Teachers - Aimed at disability professionals involved in post 16 education and the work place

20170523	UTAD, Vila Real, Portugal	Hands Free Computing	4	Accessibility Workshop	Accessibility awareness across multiple platforms	All Partners
20170328	Birmingham NEC	Hands Free Computing	4	Naidex Show 2017 - Naidex is Europe's biggest and most far-reaching trade, professional and consumer show dedicated to the care, rehabilitation, and lifestyle of people with a disability or impairment		Disability Professionals from the Educational and Industry Sectors & Impaired Users to the Beaconing Portal
20170606	Tenerife (Spain)	UCM	WP4	Gamification in medical training: from content and procedures to game-like applications	100	Researchers
20161201	Madrid	UCM	WP2	Use serious games for teacher training and use of games at the classroom	Ministry of Education	Institute for the continuous education of teachers (INTEF) Ministry of Education
20170526	Zaragoza	UCM	WP2	Use of the ICT at the classrooms	400	Teachers and practitioners
20170523	Madrid	UCM	WP2	Hackathon Junior Juegos de Salud	75	Middle School Students, Teachers
20161101	Madrid	UCM	WP2	Videojuegos Educativos y Cultura	300	Teachers in Colombia
20170602	Maya Private Middle School in Minecraft Class	SEBIT	WP5 Small Pilot	BEACONING piloted at Maya Middle School in Ankara	Playfulness in Learning Hard Math Topics	Middle School 6th Grade Maths Class
20170407	Internet	ORT France		Release of the French version of the BEACONING Presentation video		
20170301	PGC Room 2.02, Heriot-Watt University, Edinburgh, United	Heriot-Watt University		Focus group on assistive technology for STEM subject learning for students with disabilities		Users, providers, designers and researchers interested in assistive technology

	Kingdom, EH14 4AS					
20170126	British Motor Museum, Gaydon, UK	Heriot-Watt University		Applied Visualisation Forum		VR, Augmented Reality (AR) and Data Capture and Visualisation for manufacturing and training
20170613	Thiais (Paris Area), in the Lycée Guillaume Apolinaire	ORT	WP5	BEACONING Presentation to Teachers	Early Adopters	Teachers
20170523	University of Trás-os- Montes e Alto Douro (UTAD), Vila Real - Portugal	INESC TEC	WP4	BEACONING Accessibility Workshop	Enhance BEACONING accessibility	Partners developing BEACONING UI and Mini- Games
20170217	SEBIT Conference Hall, Ankara	SEBIT	WP2 Dissemination	Head Teachers Training on BEACONING	Recruiting Instructional Designers for authoring BEACONING play-lesson plans	Head Teachers, Instructional Designers
20161222	Online Webinar using Adobe Connect Virtual Classroom	SEBIT	WP2 Dissemination	BEACONING Webinar at Vitamin Teachers' Portal	Introducing game-based learning and learning analytics in BEACONING way	1000 K12 Teachers
20170403	INESC TEC, UTAD - Portugal	INESC TEC, HWU and HFC	WP4	Focus group on assistive technology at INESC TEC		
20170610	EscolaGlobal , Argoncilhe, Portugal	INESC TEC	WP7	"Digital Transformers in Education" - Microsoft Showcase Schools meeting in Portugal	Several schools are interested in experimenting when prototypes become available	K-12

20170614	CIDMA, centre for research and development in mathematics and applications, Aveiro, seminar for researchers	INESC TEC		BEACONING presented at CIDMA	Interested parties in analysing data from games	Higher Education
20170602	São João da Madeira, Portugal	INESC TEC	WP7	BEACONING at TECNET 2017	Project dissemination	Students
20170629	Bangkok, Thailand	Imaginary	Communication and Dissemination	Thaisim 2017 - Simulation and Gaming for Education	Create awareness of BEACONING and opportunities to develop games-based learning around VR and 360 video	Educators and Policy Makers in the ASEAN Region
20170608	Paris, France	ORT	WP5-WP6	BEACONING presentation to Future En Seine Stakeholders		Educational professional
20170608	Barcelona	Geomotion Games	WP2	Location-Based Serious Games - BEACONING Project		
20170322	Bacau	SIVECO Romania		Romania in spatial eLearning	Teacher involvement in the project	Teachers
20171204	REIMAGINE EDUCATION CONFERENCE & AWARDS 3-5 December 2017, PHILADELPHIA We're	ORT	WP7	Reimagining education.		

	reimagining education.					
20170616	UPTEC PINC	INESC TEC	WP4	Creative Colab 17 Education Technologies Round Table	20	Mix of Teachers, Students and Parents
20170612	Faculdade de Engenharia da Universidade do Porto	INESC TEC	WP4	Creative Colab 17 - Location-Based Games Workshop	15	Students
20170403	Universidad Complutens e de Madrid	UCM, INESC TEC	WP4	Learning Analytics Workshop	18	Developers
20170605	Tel Aviv,	ORT	WP6	BEACONING AIRBeacon concept Showcased at EdTech Summit Israel		Stakeholders
20160903	Iguassu Falls, Brazil.	BIBA - Bremer Institut für Produktion und Logistik GmbH, University of Bremen, Germany.		APMS 2016 - IFIP International Conference on Advances in Production Management Systems	Dissemination of BEACONING project	Research community
20160928	Wien, Austria.	BIBA - Bremer Institut für Produktion und Logistik GmbH, University of Bremen, Germany.		International Conference on Entertainment Computing (ICEC)	Dissemination of BEACONING project	Research community
20160821	Charlotte, North	BIBA - Bremer Institut für Produktion		International Design Engineering Technical Conferences and Computers and Information in Engineering Conference 2016	Dissemination of BEACONING project	Research community

	Carolina, USA	und Logistik GmbH, University of Bremen, Germany.				
20160421	Bucharest, Romania	BIBA - Bremer Institut für Produktion und Logistik GmbH, University of Bremen, Germany.		eLSE Conference 2016	Dissemination of BEACONING project	Research community
20161206	Utrecht, Netherlands	BIBA - Bremer Institut für Produktion und Logistik GmbH, University of Bremen, Germany.		Games and Learning Alliance International Conference	Dissemination of BEACONING project	Research community
20160511	Florida, USA	BIBA - Bremer Institut für Produktion und Logistik GmbH, University of Bremen, Germany.		4th International Conference on Serious Games and Applications for Health 2016	Dissemination of BEACONING project	Research community
20170709	Ljubljana, Slovenia	BIBA - Bremer Institut für Produktion und Logistik GmbH,		The 22nd International Symposium on Logistics (ISL 2017)	Dissemination of BEACONING project	Research community

		University of Bremen, Germany.				
20170710	Delft, Netherlands	BIBA - Bremer Institut für Produktion und Logistik GmbH, University of Bremen, Germany.		48th International Simulation and Gaming Association conference 2017	Dissemination of BEACONING project	Research community
20170918	Tsukuba City, Japan	BIBA - Bremer Institut für Produktion und Logistik GmbH, University of Bremen, Germany.		IFIP International Conference on Entertainment Computing 2017	Dissemination of BEACONING project	Research community
20170508	Internet	IFINITY		Release of the Polish version of BEACONING video		
20170206	Radio	IFINITY		BEACONING mentioned during discussion in Polish national radio		Mass audience
20170315	Beaconing website	IFINITY		Blog post on role of beacons in BEACONING		
20170317	BEACONING website	IFINITY		Example of location based activity introduced in blog post		
20170717	Scotland, Edinburgh	HWU	WP2, WP7	Invite to Immersive learning and training in construction - Construction Industry Training Board (CITB)	Unique digital pedagogy for TVET; Nation wide and at Government level which could instigate a new approach to TVET teaching and learning.	CITB, TVET, FE Colleges
20170809	August 6-9, 2017 in	HWU; BIBA	WP2; WP4; WP5; WP6; WP7	Panel Session: CIE-24-1 Advancement in Digital Technology Systems, Usage of VR and Tools for Design Engineering	Top ranking international conference on Design engineering, Technology	Industry; Engineering education; Software and Services

	Cleveland, Ohio				and Computers and Information in Industry	
20170628	Internet	IFINITY	WP4/WP2	BEACONING press release in Polish web service		
20170628	Internet	IFINITY	WP4/WP2	BEACONING press release in Polish webservice		
20170628	Internet	IFINITY	WP4/WP2	BEACONING press release in Polish webservice		
20170628	Internet	IFINITY		BEACONING press release in Polish webservice		
20170628	Internet	IFINITY		BEACONING press release in Polish webservice		
20170628	BEACONING website	IFINITY		Information about project added to Polish section of BEACONING website		